

ISic3260

I.Sicily inscription 3260

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Alex Antoniou,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Θ(εοῖς) Κ(αταχθονίοις)
2. Οὐρβανὰ ἔζησ(εν) ἔτη
3. · δ · μῆν(ας) · ς · ἡμέρ(ας) ιη
4. Οὐρβικὸς · καὶ Νίκη
5. γονεῖς · τέκνω γλυ
6. κυτάτω · ἐποίη[σ]αν

Apparatus

Korhonen 2004

Translation (eng)

To the underworld deities. Ourbana lived for 4 years, 6 months and 18 days.
Erected by her parents Ourbikos and Nike to their sweetest child.

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 493035

EDCS 28600001

PHI 316241

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. *Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin.

At 14.1919 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

Korhonen, K. 2004. Le iscrizioni del Museo civico di Catania : storia delle collezioni, cultura epigrafica, edizione. Helsinki. At 140

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